

1 **Sperm cryopreservation of *Prochilodus lineatus* throughout the same reproductive**
2 **season**

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28 ABSTRACT

29 The aim of this study was to determine the effect of seasonality on post-thaw sperm
30 quality in *Prochilodus lineatus*. Sperm from 43 males was cryopreserved throughout the
31 reproductive season (November–March). Fresh sperm quality, concentration, volume,
32 seminal plasma pH, osmolality and ion concentration were analysed. Post-thaw sperm
33 was analysed for its motility rate, velocities, beat-cross frequency, cell morphology,
34 oxidative stress and fertilization capacity. *Prochilodus lineatus* fresh sperm yielded high-
35 quality during the reproductive period (motility >80%). Post-thaw sperm quality changed
36 throughout the season, with higher motility (63.2%–72.3%) and curvilinear velocity
37 (VCL) (55.9–59.2 $\mu\text{m/s}$) from December to March. Sperm concentration was negatively
38 correlated with post-thaw sperm motility and VCL, and positively correlated with seminal
39 plasma Ca^{2+} concentration, catalase activity (CAT) and reactive oxygen species (ROS).
40 Seminal plasma Ca^{2+} was positively correlated with ROS and negatively correlated with
41 post-thaw sperm motility. Post-thaw sperm CAT and fertility correlated positively.
42 Although post-thaw sperm quality was reduced in November, the increased CAT was
43 efficient in maintaining its fertilization capacity. In order to face seasonal influence, the
44 optimal period to cryopreserve *P. lineatus* spermatozoa is from December to March, when
45 sperm exhibits characteristics which make spermatozoa more prone to resist cryodamage.

46

47 **Keywords:** CASA, neotropical fish, oxidative stress biomarkers, seminal plasma, sperm
48 concentration, spermatozoa

49

50 1. Introduction

51 The streaked prochilod *Prochilodus lineatus* (Prochilodontidae, Characiformes) is
52 a migratory neotropical fish with a large distribution in the main hydrographic basins of

53 South America, where it displays great ecological importance (Castro and Vari, 2004).
54 This species is well adapted to captivity and has been used in reproduction studies
55 (Machado et al., 2019; Miliorini et al., 2011; Paula et al., 2019), proving it can be used as
56 a model species for the study of other neotropical fish species, which are considered
57 endangered. The annual migration and spawn of the *P. lineatus* occur during the rainy
58 months when water levels rise, water temperatures are higher, and the day length is longer
59 (Vazzoler et al., 1997). During the reproductive period, *P. lineatus* male and female
60 characteristics change, and likewise, fresh gamete and seminal plasma features exhibit
61 seasonal variation (Hardt et al., 2006; Silva et al., 2009; Viveiros et al., 2019).

62 Reproduction in fish integrates the hypothalamic-pituitary gonadal axis and
63 environment information such as temperature, precipitation and photoperiod. The fish
64 brain interprets these environmental cues and transduces it into a series of physiological
65 events. The interaction among these internal and external factors influences
66 spermatogenesis and final sperm maturation (Bobe & Labbé, 2010; Bromage et al., 2001;
67 Mylonas et al., 2010). Therefore, environmental changes throughout the year and during
68 the reproductive season affect sperm quality and fertilization capacity.

69 Sperm characteristic variation throughout the reproductive period has been
70 demonstrated in teleost fish with discontinuous reproductive pattern (Johnson et al., 2013;
71 Kuradomi et al., 2016; Pires et al., 2017). Variations in sperm motility and velocities
72 during the reproductive period have been described in *Cyprinus carpio*, *Salvelinus*
73 *namaycush* and *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Cejko et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2013; Martínez-
74 Páramo et al., 2012; Martínez-Páramo, Diogo, Dinis, et al., 2012), and in *Seriola dumerili*
75 sperm velocities (Fakriadis & Mylonas, 2021). Also, changes in sperm motility and
76 straight line velocity during the reproductive season have been demonstrated in the
77 neotropical fish *Colossoma macropomum* and *Piaractus mesopotamicus* respectively

78 (Kuradomi et al., 2016; Pires et al., 2017). Variations in sperm volume and viability have
79 been reported during the reproductive period of *C. carpio* and *P. mesopotamicus* (Cejko
80 et al., 2018; Kuradomi et al., 2016). Furthermore, seasonal changes in seminal plasma
81 osmolality have been reported in *C. carpio* and *D. labrax* (Cejko et al., 2018; Martínez-
82 Páramo, Diogo, Beirão, et al., 2012), and changes in seminal plasma pH have been
83 described during the reproductive period of *C. carpio* (Cejko et al., 2018). Seasonal
84 changes in sperm concentration have been reported in *S. dumerili*, *C. carpio*, *S.*
85 *namaycush* and *D. labrax* (Cejko et al., 2018; Fakriadis & Mylonas, 2021; Johnson et al.,
86 2013; Martínez-Páramo, Diogo, Beirão, et al., 2012), and in the neotropical fish *Brycon*
87 *orbignyanus* (Viveiros, Di Chiacchio, et al., 2019). Importantly, variations of seminal
88 plasma constituents throughout the reproductive period have been associated with
89 external factors and sperm characteristics (Cejko et al., 2018; Martínez-Páramo, Diogo,
90 Beirão, et al., 2012; Viveiros, Di Chiacchio, et al., 2019)

91 The quality of initial fresh samples is recognized to influence cryopreserved sperm
92 quality (Cabrita et al., 2009). The sperm cryopreservation technique is a valuable tool that
93 can be used to provide optimal quality sperm samples, increase the availability of sperm,
94 guarantee genetic variability and biodiversity of breeders, optimize breeders management
95 and hatchery practice, simplify synchronization of gamete availability of males and
96 females, facilitate the transport of gametes and help in genetic selection programmes
97 (Asturiano et al., 2017; Cabrita et al., 2010; Judycka et al., 2019; Martínez-Páramo et al.,
98 2017; Molnár et al., 2020). This tool can be applied in the fish farming industry and
99 presents some important opportunities in the breeding of salmonid fish for aquaculture
100 (Judycka et al., 2019), and it can be also used in laboratories maintaining important strains
101 of model fish species such as *Danio rerio* and *Oryzias latipes* (Yang & Tiersch, 2009),
102 and in the conservation of threatened species to preserve genetic material, such as *Brycon*

103 *orbignyanus*, *Prochilodus vimboides* (França et al., 2020), *Esox Lucius* Cejko et al., 2020)
104 and fish from the genus *Chirostoma* (Bustamante González et al., 2021).

105 Despite its benefits and many applications, sperm cryopreservation induces
106 damages in the spermatozoon, at both structural and physiological levels (Figueroa et al.,
107 2019; Martínez-Páramo, Diogo, Dinis, et al., 2012). During sperm cryopreservation, the
108 freezing and thawing processes are responsible for the main sperm damages (Rodrigues
109 et al., 2021; Xin et al., 2020). Accordingly, the use of initial fresh samples presenting
110 good quality as well as the standardization of cryopreservation methodologies and
111 procedures is of outmost importance to guarantee the quality of post-thaw sperm (Cabrita
112 et al., 2010; Martínez-Páramo et al., 2017; Torres et al., 2016). Therefore, the assessment
113 of sperm quality associating external and internal factors that influence fresh and post-
114 thaw sperm characteristics is indispensable to guarantee the success of sperm
115 cryopreservation. In the present work, sperm from *P. lineatus* was cryopreserved
116 throughout the reproductive season and analysed with the aim to determine the effect of
117 seasonality on parameters influencing post-thaw sperm quality.

118 **2. Materials and methods**

119 *2.1. Fish handling and sperm collection*

120 The handling of animals and the experiments were carried out in strict accordance
121 with international guidelines for animal experimentation and all procedures were
122 approved by the Animal Experimentation Ethics Committee of the Federal University of
123 Lavras (UFLA), Lavras, MG, Brazil (Protocol N. 23/2018).

124 *Prochilodus lineatus* males ($n = 43$) with approximately 3 years of age were
125 selected from fish cultured in earthen ponds at the Fish Culture Station of the Agricultural
126 Research Company of Minas Gerais (EPAMIG) in the city of Leopoldina (21°28'34"S;
127 42°43'17"W), located in the Zona da Mata region, Minas Gerais State, Brazil, during the

128 spawning season 2017–2018. The fish were fed commercial extruded feed (28% crude
129 protein) twice a day ad libitum. Males (375 ± 120 g of body weight, BW) releasing a few
130 drops of sperm under soft abdominal pressure received a single intraperitoneal dose of
131 carp pituitary extract (CPE; Argent Chemical Laboratories, Redmond, USA) at 4 mg/kg
132 BW 8 h prior to sperm collection. This protocol is used in the reproduction routine to
133 induce spermiation at the Fish Culture Station.

134 Sperm was collected monthly throughout the spawning season of the species, in
135 November ($n = 7$), December ($n = 8$) (2017), January ($n = 9$), February ($n = 11$), and
136 March ($n = 8$) (2018) on the first week of each month. During the season, climate
137 conditions (temperature and precipitation) of the region were analyzed according to the
138 Brazilian National Institute of Meteorology (INMET, 2018) at Muriaé Automatic Station,
139 $21^{\circ}07'50''\text{S}; 42^{\circ}21'59''\text{W}$. The climate conditions of October were also considered as this
140 month precedes the spawning season and thus influences physiological changes on fish
141 reproductive endocrine system.

142 For sperm collection, the urogenital papilla was cleaned and dried, and
143 contamination with water, urine, feces or blood was carefully avoided. The sperm from
144 each male was collected in graduated test tubes. The volume was recorded and the sample
145 was stored in a cooler containing chemical ice ($\sim 6\text{--}9^{\circ}\text{C}$) for a maximum of 30 min.

146 *2.2. Females handling and eggs collection*

147 *Prochilodus lineatus* females ($n = 2$) with approximately 3 years of age were
148 selected at the same earthen ponds as males. Females (518 ± 22 g BW) with bulging of
149 the coelomic cavity and a protruding and reddish urogenital papilla received two
150 intraperitoneal doses of CPE at 0.5 and 5.0 mg/kg BW 20 h and 8 h prior to collection
151 respectively. This protocol is used in the reproduction routine to induce oocytes extrusion
152 at the Fish Culture Station.

153 Oocytes were collected for fertilization tests in December (2018), when females
154 presented better characteristics for spawning. For oocytes collection, the urogenital
155 papilla was cleaned and dried, and contamination with water, urine, faeces or blood was
156 carefully avoided. Oocytes were collected in dry plastic containers and weighted ($105 \pm$
157 4.24 g).

158 *2.3 Females handling and eggs collection*

159 *2.3.1 Sperm motility*

160 Fresh sperm quality was subjectively analysed by a well-trained technician.
161 Immediately after collection, each sperm sample was evaluated for motility rate
162 (expressed as the percentage of motile sperm), motility quality score (assigned using an
163 arbitrary grading system ranging from 0 to 5 – no movement to rapidly swimming sperm)
164 and duration of sperm motility (seconds) (Gonçalves et al., 2013; Viveiros & Godinho,
165 2009). Samples were analysed after activation in 150 mOsm/kg glucose solution
166 (Viveiros et al., 2016), under a light microscope (Olympus® CX22LED, Tokyo, Japan)
167 at $\times 200$ magnification. All samples yielded motility above 80%.

168 *2.3.2 Sperm concentration*

169 An aliquot of 1 μ l of sperm was diluted (1:1000) in citrate formaldehyde solution
170 (2.9% sodium citrate, 4% commercial solution of formaldehyde 35% and distilled water;
171 Vetec Química Fina, Duque de Caxias, Brazil) for posterior evaluation of sperm
172 concentration and sperm morphology (Miliorini et al., 2011). Briefly, sperm
173 concentration was determined through the observation of a 10 μ l aliquot of the diluted
174 sperm in a Neubauer-type hemocytometer chamber (Boeco, Hamburg, Germany) under
175 a light microscope (Olympus® CX22LED, Tokyo, Japan) at $\times 400$ magnification. The
176 number of sperm cells visualized on ten squares from the chamber and the dilution was
177 considered to calculate sperm concentration (Sanches et al., 2011). Fresh sperm
178 morphologic analysis was performed as described below.

179 2.3.3 Seminal plasma analysis

180 To evaluate seminal plasma, approximately 0.5 ml of each sperm sample was
181 centrifuged (K14-0602 Kasvi, São José dos Pinhais, Brazil) at 2000 g for 30 min, and the
182 collected seminal plasma (supernatant) was frozen ($-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and subsequently evaluated
183 (França et al., 2020). Seminal plasma was analysed for pH using a pH meter (DM22
184 Digimed, São Paulo, Brazil), osmolality was measured by a vapour pressure osmometer
185 (Wescor Vapro 5520, Logan, USA), and ionic composition (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) was
186 evaluated by an inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (Spectro Blue
187 ICP-OES, Kleve, Germany).

188 2.4. Sperm cryopreservation

189 Sperm from each male was individually cryopreserved within 30 min after
190 collection following the methodology described by Viveiros et al. (2009). The freezing
191 medium was composed of glucose 5% (325 mOsm/kg; pH 7.6) diluted in reverse osmosis
192 water as extender, and methyl glycol [$\text{CH}_3\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$] as cryoprotectant agent.
193 Chemicals were purchased from Vetec Química Fina (Duque de Caxias, Brazil). All
194 samples were individually diluted in the freezing medium at a ratio of 1: 8: 1 (50 μl sperm
195 (10% V/V) +400 μl extender (80% V/V) + 50 μl methyl glycol (10% V/V)) and loaded
196 into 0.5 ml straws (total of 258 straws; 43 males \times 6 replicate straws). Loaded straws were
197 kept for 10 min at room temperature (approximately 27°C) during equilibration time
198 (Viveiros et al., 2016) and placed on racks. The racks were transferred to a nitrogen
199 vapour vessel (Dry Vapor Vessel YDH-8, Cryofarm, Itu, Brazil) and straws were frozen
200 at $-170\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h (approximately $-36\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$; Maria et al., 2006), and then transferred
201 to a cryogenic tank (BioCane 34 Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dubuque, USA) at $-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
202 for storage.

203 2.5. *Post-thaw sperm analysis*

204 Post-thaw sperm analyses were carried out at the Laboratory of the Division of
205 Physiology and Pharmacology – Department of Veterinary Medicine, Federal University
206 of Lavras (UFLA) and at the Laboratory of Atherosclerosis and Biochemistry Nutritional
207 of the Biological Sciences Institute, Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG).

208 2.5.1 *Computer-Assisted Sperm Analysis (CASA)*

209 Straws ($n = 3$ straws per male) were individually thawed in a water bath (Water-bath MA
210 127, Marconi, São Paulo, Brazil) at 60°C for 8 s (Viveiros et al., 2009). Post-thaw sperm
211 features were measured using the computer-assisted sperm analysis (CASA) system,
212 following the methodology described by Viveiros et al. (2012). Briefly, sperm motility
213 was triggered in a 150 mOsm/kg glucose solution at a ratio of 1: 10 (1 μ l post-thaw sperm:
214 10 μ l activating solution) at approximately 27°C directly in a Makler™ counting chamber
215 (SefiMedical Instruments, Haifa, Israel) placed under a phase-contrast microscope
216 (Nikon™ Eclipse E200, Tokyo, Japan) at $\times 100$ magnification, green filter and phase one
217 position. The microscope was connected to a video camera (Basler Vision
218 Technologies™ A780-54FC, Ahrensburg, Germany) generating 50 images/s; video
219 recording started approximately 10 s post-activation. Each image was analysed using the
220 standard settings for fish by Sperm Class Analyzer™ software (SCA™ 2013, Microptics,
221 S.L. Version 5.4, Barcelona, Spain). Each straw was analysed in duplicate. Motility rate,
222 curvilinear velocity (VCL), average path velocity (VAP), straight line velocity (VSL) and
223 beat-cross frequency (BCF) were considered for analysis. Spermatozoon was considered
224 immotile when velocity was $< 20 \mu\text{m/s}$ of VAP. To determine these parameters, each
225 spermatozoon ($n = 1363 \pm 278$ sperm per straw) was individually followed throughout
226 the recorded video images from which sperm trajectories were evaluated. From each
227 straw thawed for CASA measurements, an aliquot of sperm was collected and diluted at

228 a ratio of 1:1000 in citrate formaldehyde solution (2.9% sodium citrate, 4% commercial
229 solution of formaldehyde 35% and distilled water; Vetec Química Fina, Duque de Caxias,
230 Brazil) for post-thaw sperm morphologic analysis. Post-thaw sperm morphologic analysis
231 was performed as described below.

232 *2.5.2 Indices of oxidative stress*

233 Post-thaw sperm samples were also assayed for oxidative stress indices and
234 antioxidant activity. Straws ($n = 2$ straws per male) were thawed in a polystyrene box
235 containing crushed ice ($5 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), and analyses were carried out on total sperm (seminal
236 plasma was not separated). The results were normalized to the total protein content,
237 determined by the Lowry method (Lowry et al., 1951).

238 The level of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) was measured as an
239 index of oxidative stress resulting from lipid peroxidation (LPO), following the protocol
240 described by Buege and Aust (1978). The absorbance of the samples was read in
241 duplicates using a microplate reader at 535 nm (Synergy 2; Bio-Tek, Winooski, USA).
242 The concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA) was read from a standard calibration curve
243 plotted using 1,1,3,3-tetramethoxypropane (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA), and the
244 results were expressed as nanomoles of MDA per milligram of protein.

245 Reactive oxygen species (ROS) content in the sperm was determined by the
246 fluorescence probe 2,7-dichlorofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA; Sigma-Aldrich, St.
247 Louis, USA) based on the method of Driver et al. (2000). A 50 mM phosphate buffer
248 solution (pH 7.2) containing DCFH-DA (final concentration $10 \mu\text{M}$) was added to the
249 samples following incubation at 37°C for 30 min. The conversion of DCFH-DA to
250 dichlorofluorescein (DCF) was measured using a microplate reader (Synergy 2, Bio-Tek,
251 Winooski, USA) at 485/530 nm (excitation/ emission), and samples were assayed in
252 duplicates. The free radical content was quantified using a DCF standard curve, and the

253 results were expressed as DCF formed per milligram of protein. Blanks containing only
254 DCFH-DA (without samples) were processed for the measurement of autofluorescence.

255 Evaluation of superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity in sperm was determined
256 based on the autoxidation of pyrogallol by the methods of Madesh and Balasubramanian
257 (1997). Samples (30 μ l) were diluted in 99 μ l of 50 mM phosphate buffer solution (pH
258 7.2), and 6 μ l of MTT (3- (4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl) -2,5-Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide;
259 Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) and 15 μ l of 1.25 mM pyrogallol (Sigma-Aldrich, St.
260 Louis, USA) were added. Blanks included all components except pyrogallol and sample.
261 The absorbance was read in duplicates using a microplate reader at 570 nm (Synergy 2;
262 BioTek, Winooski, USA). The total SOD activity was expressed in units per milligram
263 of protein, where one unit of SOD activity is defined as the amount of the enzyme
264 necessary to produce 50% dismutation of the superoxide radical per min.

265 The catalase (CAT) activity was measured according to a spectrophotometric
266 method adapted from Aebi (1984), following the decrease in absorbance at 240 nm by
267 H₂O₂ consumption. The absorbance (240 nm) was measured every 15 s for 1 min (at
268 25°C, pH 7.2 and path length 10 mm), using a quartz cuvette in a spectrophotometer
269 (Shimadzu UV-160, Kyoto, Japan), and samples were assayed in duplicates. The specific
270 activity of CAT is reported as units per milligram of protein (one unit is defined as 1 pmol
271 of H₂O₂ consumed per min).

272 *2.5.3 Fertilization tests*

273 For fertilization tests, 0.1 g oocytes (average 212 oocytes) were weighed into 50
274 mL disposable cups, and one straw from each male ($n = 43$) was thawed (60°C for 8 s)
275 and added to the cups (one straw per cup). Fresh sperm from two males was collected and
276 used as control. The mean sperm: oocyte ratio estimated was 43×10^5 spermatozoa per
277 oocyte. To activate fertilization, 5 ml of 150 mOsm/kg glucose solution (França et al.,

278 2020) was added to the cups, circular motions were performed for 90 s, and the eggs were
279 randomly transferred to experimental incubators. The incubators were arranged in a tank
280 with constant water renewal and oxygenation, where eggs remained in movement.

281 The fertilization rate was determined 8 h after fertilization when the blastopore
282 closure can be observed (Ninhaus-Silveira et al., 2006) by analysing all eggs from each
283 incubator using a trinocular stereomicroscope (Q7740SZ-T, Quimis, Diadema, Brazil) at
284 $\times 10$ magnification. The result was given by the formula: fertilization rate (%) = (number
285 of fertilized eggs/ total number of eggs) $\times 100$. The hatching rate was estimated 22 h
286 (Ninhaus-Silveira et al., 2006) after fertilization, and the result was given by the formula:
287 hatching rate (%) = (number of hatched larvae/ total number of eggs) $\times 100$.

288 *2.6. Sperm morphologic analysis*

289 Sperm morphologic analysis was performed for fresh and post-thaw sperm
290 according to Miliorini et al. (2011) methodology for this species with modifications in
291 the staining method. The diluted sample was stained with 4% Rose Bengal (3:20; stain:
292 sperm), and two wet preparations per sample were analysed (Melo-Maciel et al., 2015).
293 For each sample, two slides (a duplicate) were observed under a light microscope
294 (Olympus® CX22LED, Tokyo, Japan) at $\times 1000$ magnification, and the morphology of
295 200 sperm cells was evaluated. Primary (head degeneration, midpiece degeneration, tail
296 stump, fractured tail, strongly coiled tail, macrocephaly and microcephaly) and secondary
297 (free normal head, simple bent tail, proximal and distal droplet) damages were considered
298 (Miliorini et al., 2011). Data were recorded as the percentage of abnormal sperm cells.

299 *2.6. Statistical analysis*

300 Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Data were tested for
301 normal distribution using Shapiro–Wilk test and for significant differences using
302 ANOVA, followed by Student–Newman–Keuls test, when applicable. Possible

303 relationships among seminal plasma characteristics and post-thaw sperm features were
304 analysed by Pearson's correlation test. Statistical analyses were conducted using the R
305 software version 3.3.2 (R Development Core Team, 2016), and the level of significance
306 for all statistical tests was set to 5% ($p < 0.05$).

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309 Immediately after collection, each sperm sample was subjectively evaluated for
310 motility rate (expressed as the percentage of motile sperm), motility quality score
311 (assigned using an arbitrary grading system ranging from 0 to 5 – no movement to rapidly
312 swimming sperm) and duration of sperm motility (seconds) (Gonçalves et al., 2013;
313 Viveiros and Godinho, 2009). Samples were analyzed after activation in 150 mOsm/kg
314 glucose solution, under a light microscope (Olympus® CX22LED, Tokyo, Japan) at $\times 200$
315 magnification. All samples yielded motility above 80%.

316 An aliquot of 1 μL of sperm was diluted (1: 1000) in citrate formaldehyde solution
317 (2.9% sodium citrate, 4% commercial solution of formaldehyde 35% and distilled water;
318 Vetec Química Fina Ltd., Duque de Caxias, Brazil) for posterior evaluation of sperm
319 concentration and sperm morphology. Briefly, sperm concentration was determined
320 through the observation of a 10 μL aliquot of the diluted sperm in a Neubauer-type
321 hemacytometer chamber (Boeco, Hamburg, Germany) under a light microscope
322 (Olympus® CX22LED, Tokyo, Japan) at $\times 400$ magnification. The number of sperm cells
323 visualized on five squares from the chamber and the dilution were considered to calculate
324 sperm concentration (Sanches et al. 2011).

325 Sperm morphologic analysis was performed according to Miliorini et al. (2011)
326 methodology with slight modifications. The diluted sample was stained with 4% Rose
327 Bengal (3: 20; stain: sperm) and two wet preparations per sample were analyzed (Melo-
328 Maciel et al., 2015). For each sample, two slides (a duplicate) were observed under a light

329 microscope (Olympus® CX22LED, Tokyo, Japan) at ×1000 magnification and the
330 morphology of 200 sperm cells was evaluated. Primary (head degeneration, midpiece
331 degeneration, tail stump, fractured tail, strongly coiled tail, macrocephaly, and
332 microcephaly) and secondary (free normal head, simple bent tail, proximal, and distal
333 droplet) damages were considered (Miliorini et al., 2011). Data were recorded as the
334 percentage of abnormal sperm cells.

335 To evaluate seminal plasma, approximately 0.5 mL of each sperm sample was
336 centrifuged (K14-0602 Kasvi, São José dos Pinhais, Brazil) at 2000 ×g for 30 min. The
337 seminal plasma (supernatant) was collected and frozen (−20°C) to be subsequently
338 evaluated. Seminal plasma was analyzed for pH using a pH meter (DM22 Digimed, São
339 Paulo, Brazil), osmolality by a vapor pressure osmometer (Wescor Vapro 5520, Logan,
340 USA), and ionic composition (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+}) by an inductively coupled plasma
341 optical emission spectrometer (Spectro Blue ICP-OES, Kleve, Germany).

342 *2.3. Sperm cryopreservation*

343 Sperm from each male was individually cryopreserved within 30 min after
344 collection following the methodology described by Viveiros et al. (2009). Briefly, the
345 freezing medium was composed of 325 mOsm/kg glucose solution (pH 7.6) as the
346 extender and methyl glycol [$\text{CH}_3\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$] as the cryoprotectant agent. Chemicals
347 were purchased from Vetec Química Fina Ltd. (Duque de Caxias, Brazil). Sperm was
348 diluted in the freezing medium to a ratio of 1 sperm: 8 extender: 1 cryoprotectant and
349 loaded into 0.5 mL straws (total of 258 straws; 43 males × 6 replicate straws), followed
350 by an equilibration time of 10 min at room temperature (approximately 27 °C) (Viveiros
351 et al., 2016). Straws were frozen in a nitrogen vapor vessel (Dry Vapor Vessel YDH-8,
352 Cryofarm, Itu, Brazil) at −170°C for 24h (approximately −36°C/min; Maria et al., 2006),

353 and then transferred to a cryogenic tank (BioCane 34 Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dubuque,
354 USA) at -196°C for storage.

355 *2.4. Post-thaw sperm analysis*

356 Post-thaw sperm analyses were carried out at the Laboratory of the Division of
357 Physiology and Pharmacology – Department of Veterinary Medicine, Federal University
358 of Lavras (UFLA) and at the Laboratory of Atherosclerosis and Biochemistry Nutritional
359 of the Biological Sciences Institute, Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG).

360 *2.4.1. Computer-Assisted Sperm Analysis (CASA)*

361 Straws ($n = 3$ straws per male) were individually thawed in a water bath (Water-
362 bath MA 127, Marconi, São Paulo, Brazil) at 60°C for 8 s (Viveiros et al., 2009). Post-
363 thaw sperm features were estimated using the Computer-Assisted Sperm Analysis
364 (CASA) system, following the methodology described by Viveiros et al. (2012). Briefly,
365 sperm motility was triggered in a 150 mOsm/kg glucose solution at a ratio of 1: 10 (1 μl
366 post-thaw sperm: 10 μl activating solution) at approximately 27°C directly in a Makler™
367 counting chamber (Sefi-Medical Instruments Ltd., Haifa, Israel) placed under a phase-
368 contrast microscope (Nikon™ Eclipse E200, Tokyo, Japan) at $\times 100$ magnification, green
369 filter and phase one position. The microscope was connected to a video camera (Basler
370 Vision Technologies™ A780-54FC, Ahrensburg, Germany) generating 50 images/s;
371 video recording started approximately 10 s post-activation. Each image was analyzed
372 using the standard settings for fish by Sperm Class Analyzer™ software (SCA™ 2013,
373 Microptics, S.L. Version 5.4, Barcelona, Spain). Motility rate, curvilinear velocity
374 (VCL), average path velocity (VAP), straight line velocity (VSL), and beat-cross
375 frequency (BCF) were considered for analysis. Spermatozoon was considered immotile
376 when velocity was $< 20 \mu\text{m/s}$ of VAP. To determine these parameters, each spermatozoon
377 ($n = 1363 \pm 278$ sperm per straw) was individually followed throughout the recorded

378 video images from which sperm trajectories were evaluated. From each thawed straw, an
379 aliquot of sperm was diluted at a ratio of 1: 1000 in citrate formaldehyde solution for post-
380 thaw sperm morphologic analysis, performed as described for fresh sperm.

381 *2.4.2. Indices of oxidative stress*

382 Post-thaw sperm samples were also assayed for oxidative stress indices and
383 antioxidant activity. Straws ($n = 2$ straws per male) were thawed in a polystyrene box
384 containing crushed ice ($5 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and analyses were carried out on total sperm (seminal
385 plasma was not separated). The results were normalized to the total protein content,
386 determined by the Lowry method (Lowry et al., 1951).

387 The level of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) was measured as an
388 index of oxidative stress resulting from lipid peroxidation (LPO), following the protocol
389 described by Buege and Aust (1978). The absorbance of the samples was read in
390 duplicates using a microplate reader at 535 nm (Synergy 2; BioTek, Winooski, USA).
391 The concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA) was read from a standard calibration curve
392 plotted using 1,1,3,3-tetramethoxypropane (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA), and the
393 results were expressed as nanomoles of MDA per milligram of protein.

394 Reactive oxygen species (ROS) content in the sperm was determined by the
395 fluorescence probe 2,7-dichlorofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA; Sigma Aldrich, St.
396 Louis, USA) based on the method of Driver et al. (2000). A 50 mM phosphate buffer
397 solution (pH 7.2) containing DCFH-DA (final concentration 10 μM) was added to the
398 samples following incubation at 37°C for 30 min. The conversion of DCFH-DA to
399 dichlorofluorescein (DCF) was measured using a microplate reader (Synergy 2, BioTek,
400 Winooski, USA) at 485/530 nm (excitation/ emission), samples were assayed in
401 duplicates. The free radical content was quantified using a DCF standard curve and the

402 results were expressed as DCF formed per milligram of protein. Blanks containing only
403 DCFH-DA (without samples) were processed for the measurement of autofluorescence.

404 Evaluation of superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity in sperm was determined
405 based on the autoxidation of pyrogallol by the methods of Madesh and Balasubramanian
406 (1997). Samples (30 μ L) were diluted in 99 μ L of 50 mM phosphate buffer solution (pH
407 7.2), and 6 μ L of MTT (3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide;
408 Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) and 15 μ L of 1.25 mM pyrogallol (Sigma-Aldrich, St.
409 Louis, USA) were added. Blanks included all components except pyrogallol and sample.
410 The absorbance was read in duplicates using a microplate reader at 570 nm (Synergy 2;
411 Bio-Tek, Winooski, USA). The total SOD activity was expressed in units per milligram
412 of protein, where one unit of SOD activity is defined as the amount of the enzyme
413 necessary to produce 50% dismutation of the superoxide radical per min.

414 The catalase (CAT) activity was measured according to a spectrophotometric
415 method adapted from Aebi (1984), following the decrease in absorbance at 240 nm by
416 H₂O₂ consumption. The absorbance (240 nm) was measured every 15 s for 1 min (at 25°C,
417 pH 7.2 and path length 10 mm), using a quartz cuvette in a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu
418 UV-160, Kyoto, Japan), samples were assayed in duplicates. The specific activity of CAT
419 is reported as units per milligram of protein (one unit is defined as 1 pmol of H₂O₂
420 consumed per minute).

421 2.4.3. Fertilization tests

422 For fertilization tests, oocytes were collected in December (2018), when females
423 presented better characteristics for spawning. Oocytes were collected in dry plastic
424 containers, 0.1 g oocytes was weighed into 50 mL disposable cups, and sperm was thawed
425 (60°C for 8 s) and added to the cups (one straw per cup). Fresh sperm from two males
426 was collected and used as control. To activate fertilization, 5 mL of 150 mOsm/kg glucose

427 solution (França et al., 2020) was added to the cups, circular motions were performed for
428 90 s, and the oocytes were randomly transferred to experimental incubators. The
429 incubators were arranged in a tank with constant water renewal and oxygenation, where
430 oocytes remained in movement.

431 The fertilization rate was determined 8 h after fertilization when the blastopore
432 closure can be observed (Ninhaus-Silveira et al., 2006) by analyzing all oocytes from
433 each incubator using a trinocular stereomicroscope (Q7740SZ-T, Quimis, Diadema,
434 Bazil) at $\times 10$ magnification. The result was given by the formula: fertilization rate (%) =
435 (number of fertilized oocytes/ total number of oocytes) $\times 100$. The hatching rate was
436 estimated 22 h (Ninhaus-Silveira et al., 2006) after fertilization and the result was given
437 by the formula: hatching rate (%) = (number of hatched larvae/ total number of oocytes)
438 $\times 100$.

439 2.5. Statistical analysis

440 Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Data were tested for
441 normal distribution using Shapiro–Wilk test and for significant differences using
442 ANOVA, followed by Student–Newman–Keuls test, when applicable. Possible
443 relationships among seminal plasma characteristics and post-thaw sperm features were
444 analyzed by Pearson's correlation test. Statistical analyses were conducted using the R
445 software version 3.3.2 (R Development Core Team, 2016) and the level of significance
446 for all statistical tests was set to 5% ($P < 0.05$).

447 3. Results

448 3.1. Fresh sperm analysis and characterization of seminal plasma

449 *Prochilodus lineatus* mean sperm volume (0.60–0.99 ml) was similar throughout
450 the reproductive season, whereas concentration values were higher in November (44.34
451 ± 8.59 spermatozoa $\times 10^9$ /ml) than the other months studied (15.87–20.35 spermatozoa

452 $\times 10^9/\text{ml}$, December to March) (Table S1). Fresh sperm yielded similar motility rates
453 (86.25%–90.00%) throughout the reproductive season. The motility quality score was
454 significantly higher in November, January and February (4.73–5.00), and the duration of
455 motility was higher in January (348.11 ± 117.74 s).

456 Seminal plasma pH was higher in February than in January, and
457 plasma osmolality presented no significant difference among the months (Table 1). The
458 ionic composition of the seminal plasma fluctuated during the season (Table 1).

459 3.2. Post-thaw sperm analysis

460 *Prochilodus lineatus* post-thaw sperm yielded higher motility rates (63.18%–
461 72.35%) from December to March (Figure 1a), and sperm VCL (46.49–59.19 $\mu\text{m/s}$) was
462 higher in samples cryopreserved in January and February than in November (Figure 1b).
463 Post-thaw sperm VAP, VSL and BCF were similar among the months (32.66–38.38 $\mu\text{m/s}$
464 of VAP, 22.51–24.61 $\mu\text{m/s}$ of VSL and 3.04–3.18 Hz of BCF) (Figure 1b,c).

465 The highest CAT activity values (Table 2) accompanied the lowest sperm motility
466 in November, whereas LPO, ROS and the SOD activity values presented no significant
467 difference throughout the season (Table 2).

468 Post-thaw sperm fertilization (7.34%–22.32%) and hatching (5.37%–14.47%)
469 rates presented no significant difference throughout the reproductive season (Figure 2).
470 Considerable variation in fertilization and hatching rates was observed among
471 individuals, as evidenced by the large standard deviations in these samples. Fresh sperm
472 fertilization ($40.79 \pm 10.20\%$) and hatching ($26.32 \pm 6.10\%$) rates yielded intermediate
473 results (Figure 2).

474 Sperm concentration was positively correlated with Ca^{2+} concentration on seminal
475 plasma ($r = 0.81$; $p < 0.01$), with the oxidative stress-related parameters of ROS levels (r
476 $= 0.45$; $p < 0.01$) and with CAT activity ($r = 0.40$; $p < 0.01$), and negative correlations

477 were observed between sperm concentration and sperm motility ($r = -0.54$; $p < 0.01$) and
478 VCL ($r = -0.41$; $p < 0.01$) (Table S2). The concentration of Ca^{2+} on seminal plasma was
479 positively correlated with ROS levels ($r = 0.59$; $p < 0.05$), whereas negatively correlated
480 with sperm motility ($r = -0.68$; $p < 0.01$). A significant correlation was positive between
481 CAT activity and fertilization rate ($r = 0.32$; $p < 0.05$).

482 3.3. Sperm morphologic analysis

483 Regarding the fresh sperm morphological analysis, the percentage of normal cells
484 observed in February ($90.43 \pm 3.99\%$) was higher than in March ($83.56 \pm 3.39\%$). Values
485 of primary damages observed in February ($6.84 \pm 3.53\%$) were lower than in March
486 ($10.88 \pm 2.35\%$), while the lowest values of secondary damages were observed in
487 November, January and February (2.73% – 3.50%) (Table S1).

488 In respect to post-thaw sperm morphology, significantly less normal sperm cells
489 were observed in samples cryopreserved in March ($72.06 \pm 2.49\%$) (Figure 3). The lowest
490 primary damages values were observed in samples from December to February (11.21 –
491 13.78%). Secondary damages were higher in March ($8.94 \pm 2.04\%$) than in February
492 ($5.07 \pm 1.56\%$).

493

494

495 4. Discussion

496 The effects of cryopreservation on fish sperm have been addressed by different
497 authors (Figueroa et al., 2019; Paula et al., 2019; Shaliutina-Kolešová et al., 2015; Wang
498 et al., 2016) with the objective to improve the use of this tool. In the present work, the
499 association between techniques to study *Prochilodus lineatus* postthaw sperm throughout
500 the reproductive season permitted a better understanding of sperm physiology. Our
501 findings showed that seasonal variations of sperm characteristics influenced the effects

502 of the freezing and thawing process on sperm function, thus affecting post-thaw sperm
503 quality.

504 Although it is described that the reproductive season of the *P. lineatus* ends in
505 January or February (Silva et al., 2009; Vazzoler et al., 1997), both fresh and post-thaw
506 sperm presented good motility rates in March. This suggests that the reproductive season
507 of this species may be extended. Furthermore, our group has observed *P. lineatus* females
508 presenting external characteristics linked to reproductive activity in March, and Hardt et
509 al. (2006) also reported physiological characteristics linked to reproductive capability at
510 this time of the year for this species. Among October and March, precipitation values
511 presented a total mean of 197.67 ± 108.13 mm a month, and precipitation levels were
512 higher in March (total mean of 344 ± 20.29 mm) and lower in October (13 ± 1.12 mm)
513 than in the other months analysed (180–246 mm) (Brazilian National Institute and of
514 Meteorology (INMET), 2018). The high precipitation levels registered in March may
515 have influenced fish reproductive activity, since rainfall plays a key role in changing
516 water characteristics such as water depths and water physical–chemical conditions, which
517 are important environmental cues to fish reproduction (Godinho et al., 2017; Lopes et al.,
518 2018; Stassen et al., 2010).

519 In addition to rainfall, environmental temperature also influences fish
520 reproduction (Bobe & Labbé, 2010; Mylonas et al., 2010). During this study, the average
521 daily minimum and maximum temperatures were 21.15 and 30.03°C, respectively, with
522 a mean of 25.59 ± 5.20 °C (Brazilian National Institute and of Meteorology (INMET),
523 2018), which are within the expected temperature range for the period.

524 Seminal plasma pH, osmolality and composition (ions, lipids, proteins, enzymes)
525 are essential to spermatozoa protection and metabolism, and influence reproductive
526 success in both natural and artificial spawning (Dietrich et al., 2019; Kowalski & Cejko,

2019; Lahnsteiner, 2007; Lahnsteiner & Mansour et al., 2010). Although seminal plasma osmolality and pH are important sperm quality indicators (Kowalski & Cejko, 2019), these parameters were not associated with the other sperm quality markers evaluated in this work. The maintenance of seminal plasma osmolality and pH between 296.33–350.40 mOsm/kg, and 8.45–8.95, respectively, during the season characterizes the values usually observed for the species (Viveiros, Di Chiacchio, et al., 2019; Viveiros et al., 2016), thus providing a good environment for spermatozoa performance. The ionic composition of *P. lineatus* seminal plasma fluctuated throughout the reproductive period, and this has also been reported by Viveiros, Di Chiacchio, et al. (2019) in this species and in *Brycon orbignyanus*, whereas Kuradomi et al. (2016) found no differences in *Piaractus mesopotamicus*.

The quality of fresh samples is known to influence cryopreserved sperm quality (Cabrita et al., 2009). In the present study, although *P. lineatus* yielded high-quality fresh sperm throughout the reproductive season (motility above 80%) (Kowalski & Cejko, 2019), post-thaw sperm quality changed during the season. In contrast to the present findings, Di Chiacchio et al. (2017) detected no differences in *P. lineatus* post-thaw sperm motility rate and velocities during the reproductive period. During the reproductive season, no differences were reported for fresh sperm motility rate in *Seriola dumerili* (Fakriadis & Mylonas, 2021), and in *Colossoma macropomum* (Pires et al., 2017). On the other hand, *Piaractus mesopotamicus* fresh sperm presented higher motility rate in the beginning and middle of the reproductive period (Kuradomi et al., 2016), while *Cyprinus carpio* and *Dicentrarchus labrax* fresh sperm yielded higher motility rate at the end of the season (Cejko et al., 2018; Martínez-Páramo, Diogo, Beirão, et al., 2012).

In this study, *P. lineatus* post-thaw sperm quality was influenced by sperm concentration, which was higher in November. Since higher sperm concentrations are

552 associated with reduced post-thaw sperm quality due to lower availability of the
553 cryoprotectant within the spermatozoa (Torres et al., 2016), it is possible that the samples
554 cryopreserved in November did not have optimal cryoprotectant availability. The
555 presence of seminal plasma components is also important during sperm cryopreservation
556 (Wang et al., 2016). Hence, the higher sperm concentration may also have caused a
557 decrease in the availability of seminal plasma constituents, particularly its antioxidant
558 components. This contributed to the lower sperm motility rate and VCL registered in
559 November.

560 Sperm cryopreservation induces oxidative stress, increasing ROS generation and
561 reducing post-thaw sperm quality due to LPO of sperm membranes and oxidative DNA
562 damage (Figuerola et al., 2018, 2019; Martínez-Páramo, Diogo, Dinis, et al., 2012;
563 Shaliutina-Kolešová et al., 2015). In fish, seminal plasma represents the major source of
564 sperm defence system against oxidative stress (Lahnsteiner & Mansour, 2010). Thus, the
565 reduced availability of the seminal plasma antioxidant system in November produced an
566 imbalance between cell generation of ROS and sperm antioxidants, leading to oxidative
567 stress-related damage. This agrees with the correlation analysis data, which identified a
568 positive correlation between sperm concentration and ROS levels.

569 The positive correlation of Ca^{2+} concentration in seminal plasma with ROS levels,
570 and the negative correlation between this ion and post-thaw sperm motility rate indicate
571 that the interaction of these agents disturbed spermatozoa metabolism. The negative
572 effects of Ca^{2+} on sperm motility have been demonstrated in characiforms and cyprinids
573 (França et al., 2020; Khara et al., 2014; Viveiros et al., 2019). The freezing and thawing
574 process disturb the mitochondrial oxidative metabolism, leading to enhanced ROS
575 generation and dysregulation of mitochondrial Ca^{2+} homeostasis, which in turn stimulates
576 an increase in mitochondrial oxidative metabolism, resulting in mitochondrial

577 dysfunction, impairment of ATP synthesis (Brookes et al., 2004) and ultimately loss of
578 post-thaw sperm motility (Figuroa et al., 2016, 2019). Thus, the results in the present
579 study reinforce the importance of the interaction between ROS and Ca²⁺ in the
580 mitochondria for sperm physiology. Furthermore, these results indicate that cryodamage
581 affected sperm plasma membrane and the calcium-binding proteins present in it, which
582 are important in the regulation of sperm motility (Cosson, 2019; Kholodnyy et al., 2020;
583 Yoshida & Asturiano, 2020).

584 Antioxidant enzyme activity is known to increase to oppose the peroxidation of
585 lipids in sperm (Martínez-Páramo, Diogo, Dinis, et al., 2012; Shaliutina-Kolešová et al.,
586 2018). Consequently, sperm CAT activity increased in November due to a need for a
587 higher defensive response against oxidative stress. In fish sperm, CAT acts as an
588 important agent to mitigate the negative effects of oxidative stress (Hagedorn et al., 2012).
589 The increase in CAT activity in response to oxidative stress while SOD activity did not
590 change indicates that CAT is an important antioxidant agent for *P. lineatus* sperm.
591 Similarly, no changes were reported in sperm SOD activity during the reproductive period
592 of *C. carpio* and *O. mykiss* (Shaliutina-Kolešová et al., 2018)

593 Post-thaw sperm ROS and LPO did not vary significantly among the months. This
594 suggests that the increase in CAT activity in November was capable to oppose LPO by
595 reducing ROS to lower levels. Nevertheless, CAT could not block the damages caused
596 by ROS in the spermatozoa, resulting in decreased sperm motility and VCL in samples
597 cryopreserved in November. Increased sperm LPO was reported at the beginning of the
598 reproductive season in *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Martínez-Páramo, Diogo, Beirão, et al.,
599 2012), while in *Cyprinus carpio* and *Oncorhynchus mykiss* it was higher at the end of the
600 season (Shaliutina-Kolešová et al., 2018).

601 Post-thaw sperm fertilization rates also did not present significant differences
602 throughout the reproductive season. It is possible that the increased CAT antioxidant
603 activity at the beginning of the season restrained some of the adverse effects of ROS on
604 the spermatozoa, ensuring these cells fertilization ability, which was positively correlated
605 with CAT activity. Fertilization tests were performed with fresh sperm for control
606 purposes and yielded intermediate results. Post-thaw sperm yielded low fertilization rates,
607 despite good sperm motility and velocities, which are features correlated with sperm
608 fertility (Figuroa et al., 2016; Gallego & Asturiano, 2018). This indicates a detrimental
609 effect of oocytes on fertilization, although the eggs exhibited external characteristics of
610 good quality (slightly greyish eggs, translucent, granular-looking, and not watery).

611 Spermatozoa morphology affects sperm motility and fertilizing capacity (Murgas
612 et al., 2011), and other studies also reported seasonal variations on fish sperm morphology
613 (Damasceno et al., 2015; Kuradomi et al., 2016). In this study, midpiece degeneration
614 was the most observed damage in post-thaw spermatozoa (data not shown). Structural
615 alterations in the midpiece are considered to negatively affect sperm fertilizing capacity
616 due to its association with mitochondrial dysfunction (Figuroa et al., 2019; Miliorini et
617 al., 2011). However, spermatozoa morphological alterations were not associated with
618 sperm fertility in this work. This might be related to the percentage of total damages
619 observed in post-thaw samples (16.27%–27.94%), since the critical proportion of fish
620 sperm abnormalities for artificial fecundation is considered to be around 50% (Miliorini
621 et al., 2011).

622 The quality of *P. lineatus* post-thaw sperm was influenced by sperm
623 concentration, oxidative stress-related damage and seminal plasma ionic composition.
624 The association between techniques to assess sperm characteristics proved to be
625 important in order to improve the knowledge on the mechanisms by which the

626 cryopreservation process affects the sperm, thus permitting the management of the factors
627 influencing sperm quality. Although fresh sperm presented good quality throughout the
628 reproductive season, the quality of cryopreserved sperm showed seasonal variations. In
629 this study, we identified that in order to face seasonal influence, the optimal period to
630 cryopreserve *P. lineatus* spermatozoa is from December to March, when sperm exhibits
631 better characteristics to undergo the stress induced by cryopreservation.

632

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 655 & Editing. **Luis D.S. Murgas:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Project
 656 administration, Resources, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing.

657

658 **Declarations of interest**

659 The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest that could be perceived as
 660 prejudicing the impartiality of the research reported.

661

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987 **Tables**

988 Table 1. Characteristics of the seminal plasma of *Prochilodus lineatus* throughout the
 989 reproductive season (from November to March). The ionic concentrations of Na⁺, K⁺,
 990 Ca²⁺ e Mg²⁺ ions (mmol/L = mM) were determined by an inductively coupled plasma
 991 optical emission spectrometer.

Month	<i>n</i>	Osmolality (mOsm/kg)	pH	Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	K ⁺ (mmol/L)	Ca ²⁺ (mmol/L)	Mg ²⁺ (mmol/L)
NOV	7	350.40±5.81	8.56±0.10 ^{ab}	51.55±1.26 ^a	32.31±0.53 ^c	0.91±0.13 ^b	4.68±0.67 ^a
DEC	8	296.33±78.50	8.63±0.08 ^{ab}	40.49±0.36 ^c	35.18±0.34 ^b	2.03±0.00 ^a	1.31±0.01 ^b
JAN	9	350.25±12.76	8.45±0.16 ^b	41.60±1.01 ^c	32.92±0.91 ^c	0.92±0.00 ^b	1.10±0.01 ^b
FEB	11	333.86±7.38	8.95±0.28 ^a	44.37±0.87 ^b	41.19±0.26 ^a	0.44±0.00 ^d	1.35±0.00 ^b
MAR	8	323.00±4.32	8.55±0.25 ^{ab}	29.03±0.42 ^d	24.43±0.43 ^d	0.55±0.00 ^c	1.08±0.01 ^b

992 Different superscripts in the same row show differences between months for each
 993 parameter tested (ANOVA-SNK, $P < 0.05$, mean values ± SD).

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1006 Table 2. Indices of oxidative stress in *Prochilodus lineatus* sperm cryopreserved
 1007 throughout the reproductive season (from November to March).

Month	<i>n</i>	LPO (nmol-MDA/ mg-protein)	ROS (DCF-fluorescence/ mg-protein)	SOD (U-SOD/mg- protein)	CAT (U-CAT/mg- protein)
NOV	7	0.39±0.15	7.06±3.89	1.69±0.62	3.92±1.95 ^a
DEC	8	0.30±0.06	5.68±2.89	1.49±0.24	0.64±0.63 ^b
JAN	9	0.39±0.12	5.58±2.33	1.84±0.46	1.28±1.25 ^b
FEB	11	0.32±0.12	4.06±1.83	1.40±0.18	1.84±1.95 ^b
MAR	8	0.31±0.11	5.22±2.68	1.51±0.38	2.05±1.21 ^b

1008 Different superscripts in the same row show differences between months for each
 1009 parameter tested (ANOVA-SNK, $P < 0.05$, mean values \pm SD). LPO: lipid peroxidation;
 1010 MDA: malondialdehyde; ROS: reactive oxygen species; DCF: dichlorofluorescein; SOD:
 1011 superoxide dismutase enzyme; CAT: catalase enzyme.

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1025 **Figures**

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1027 Figure 1. Motility rate (a) curvilinear velocity (VCL), average path velocity (VAP),
 1028 straight line velocity (VSL) (b) and beat-cross frequency (BCF) (c) of *Prochilodus*
 1029 *lineatus* sperm cryopreserved throughout the reproductive season, in November (n = 7),
 1030 December (n = 8), January (n = 9), February (n = 11) and March (n = 8). Data correspond
 1031 to mean values \pm SD. Different letters show differences between months for each
 1032 parameter (ANOVA-SNK, $p < 0.05$).

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1035 Figure 2. Fertilization and hatching rates of *Prochilodus lineatus* sperm cryopreserved
 1036 throughout the reproductive season, in November (n = 7), December (n = 8), January (n
 1037 = 9), February (n = 11) and March (n = 8). Data correspond to mean values \pm SD
 1038 (ANOVA-SNK, $p < 0.05$).

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1046 Figure 3. Morphology of *Prochilodus lineatus* sperm cryopreserved throughout the
 1047 reproductive season, in November (n = 7), December (n = 8), January (n = 9), February
 1048 (n = 11) and March (n = 8). Data correspond to mean values \pm SD. Different letters show
 1049 differences between months for each parameter (ANOVA-SNK, $p < 0.05$).